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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK K bearing USN 6SU21RT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsABIN ANIL bearing USN 6SU21RT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsADIL M A bearing USN 6SU21RT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEENA DEEPAK bearing USN 6SU21RT004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsASHIN JITHEESH bearing USN 6SU21RT005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA NAFIA bearing USN 6SU21RT006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGOPIKA K V bearing USN 6SU21RT007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARINARAYANAN V R bearing USN 6SU21RT008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsHEERA P V bearing USN 6SU21RT009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsKEERTHANA P bearing USN 6SU21RT010has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMALAVIKA K G bearing USN 6SU21RT011has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MISHAB SHAH K P bearing USN 6SU21RT012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED KHAIF N bearing USN 6SU21RT013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ANAS bearing USN 6SU21RT014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED MUSTHAFA bearing USN 6SU21RT015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRATHIKSHA V POOJARI bearing USN 6SU21RT016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RIBINA KABEER V T bearing USN 6SU21RT017 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMMAS K V bearing USN 6SU21RT018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHILNA MACHA P T bearing USN 6SU21RT019 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHRAVYA bearing USN 6SU21RT020 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSREELAKSHMI VIJAYAN bearing USN 6SU21RT021 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA DILSHA T.T bearing USN 6SU21RT022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KAMAL HATHIM V K bearing USN 6SU21RT023 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED NAVAS A bearing USN 6SU21RT024 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU ASHOK bearing USN 6SU21RT025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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